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COVID-19 Special Issue-I

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Public Health Challenges and Management during the COVID-19 Outbreak in Odisha

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the management of COVID-19 by the Government of Odisha by focusing on problems related to lockdown, isolation, quarantine and hospitals beds in Odisha and its neighbouring states. The state government has initiated various measures to contain the spread of the infection through effective engagement of health workers and information sharing in wider media. This might have resulted in a low case confirmation ratio, low case fatality rate, and a greater recovery and discharge ratio. However, there remains many more challenges before the administration and public health authorities.

Keywords: Hospital beds, Management, Pandemic, Public health, Quarantine, Odisha

Introduction

An incredibly contagious disease COVID-19 has affected over a million and has caused over 606 thousand deaths world wide. In India, it has infected 1.1 million people and around 27000 of them had died by mid-July 2020 (Parmar, 2020). The pandemic has created several constraints including the required changes in provision of care in hospitals as numerous non-COVID patients

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have deferred their treatment. The lockdown has also adversely affected people in different ways (Hebbar et al., 2020).

Odisha had taken proactive steps in creating wide spread awareness through campaigns and press meets on social distancing and concerned restrictions at community, district and village levels often involving local level institutions as the Panchayats. Its activities included testing, separating the infected and setting up of COVID emergency hospitals. The state rejigged the working of the healthcare set-ups with web-based training programs and even sent experts to remote areas on COVID duty (Pattnaik et al., 2020). The administration played a major role in controlling the transmission and also in financing of testing and other healthcare provisioning for the infected. Because of the announcement of national lockdown and the advance preventive steps taken by the state government, the situation of Odisha is presently better than that of some other major Indian states (Ganguly et al., 2020; Pattnaik et al., 2020).

The pandemic has posed a challenge not only to the public health system but demands financial allocations of unexpected proportions that threatens availability of funds for other ailments and long term health concerns (V. Sharma, 2020). Estimates of recovery due to the lockdown suggest that Odisha's performance was relatively better, including in managing the return-migrants (A. Das, 2020; S. Das, 2020; Priyambada et al., 2020). This paper focuses on the management of COVID-19 by the state government with reference to issues in lockdown, quarantine and hospitals beds in Odisha.

The COVID-19 Scenario in India and Odisha

As shown in Figure 1, by June 31, 2020 when India's COVID-19 cases stood at 1.04 million with 26,295 deaths in Odisha these figures were 16701 and 86, respectively. This implied the fatality rate of 0.33 per cent for Odisha and 4.82 per cent for India (Kazmi et al., 2020). As of mid July 2020, the recovery rate for Odisha was 61.38 per cent as against the same for India being 1.83 per cent. In Odisha, the death rate was 0.45 per cent whereas for India it was 1.61 per cent. Further, while the total tests per million was 0.38 for Odisha it was 7.4 at the national level. Importantly, deaths per million was much lower at 0.33 for Odisha as against 4.82 in India (HFWO, 2020a & b). Since the start, the state's response to the pandemic has been pragmatic with extensive testing, effective asset allotment, quick private sector associations, setting up healthcare infrastructure, etc.

Figure 1: COVID-19 Related Figures for India and Odishaby Mid-July 2020

Source: Computed by authors

The pandemic has upended these lives of people as major health facilities are closed, borders are sealed, schools are closed and businesses are shut, resulting in a global public health challenge. Although research and trials were being performed by scientists to find a treatment or vaccine for COVID-19, it is evident that the country's present public health system was not equipped to deal with the issue (S. Sharma, 2020). The first and most challenging aspect is the availability of testing kits, medical supplies, Personal Protective Equipments (PPEs) and its timely distribution. Although there are qualified doctors, paramedics and nurses, they are not well equipped to prepare for and respond to the pandemic. Similarly, the hospitals in India lack Intensive Care Unit (ICU) facilities, isolation wards and medicines to treat COVID-19 (Saikia, 2017). Additionally, due to the limited coordination between the three tiers of government, namely, the federal, provincial and local the problem of poor recording and reporting is possible (Kazmi et al., 2020). While everyone seems to be more focused on how to treat or control COVID-19 cases, other important public health priority programs are at the risk of being ignored. In this regard,

international public health experts have expressed their concern that the focus on COVID-19 cases would only delay the treatment of other medical issues or the provision of vaccinations for diseases such as measles (Pattnaik et al., 2020). As the lockdown continued, a sense of fear and confusion might rise among the general population regarding COVID-19 (Iriart & Merhy, 2012).

COVID-19 Healthcare Facilities in Odisha

The COVID-19 hospitals/care centres are operational in 16 out of 30 districts in Odisha. The special hospitals are situated in different districts such as Gajapati, Ganjam, Jajapur, Keonjhar, Khurda, Puri, Cuttack, Sundargarh, Bhadrak, Rayagada, Malkangiri, Dhenkanal, Boudh, Kendrapara, Balasore and Koraput regions. There are about 7,020 Temporary Medical Centres (TMCs) with the 62,659 bed capacity being functional in all the 6,798 Gram Panchayats across the state (Jena, 2020). There has been a good stock of three-layer veils, N-95 masks, PPEs and hand sanitizers. Further, equipments like ICU ventilators, oxygen concentrators and nebulizers have been available. The proposed expansion in terms of infrastructure for COVID care by the state government involves 500-bed isolation wards in each district, including 50-bed ICUs equipped with ventilators in government hospitals to manage the emerging situation (Mohanty, 2020; Muduli & Barve, 2012). The 30 districts of the state have been placed under three revenue divisions to restructure their governance.

Table 1 shows the healthcare beds availability in the northern division of the state. In terms of most parameters Sambalpur is much better placed compared to other districts.

Table 1: COVID-19 Healthcare Beds Availability in Northern Division of Odisha

District	Number of beds per TMC	Number of beds per centre	Difference of beds capacity and total beds	ICU beds per centre	Isolation beds per centre	Number of ventilator beds per centre	Oxygen beds per centre
Anugul	35.53	200.00	-50.00	5.00	72.00	2.00	18.00
Balangir	68.59	126.67	73.33	3.33	63.33	3.33	6.67
Bargarh	56.66	76.67	123.33	2.67	30.67	1.67	12.00
Deogarh	30.66	178.00	32.00	0.00	103.00	0.00	46.00
Dhenkanal	49.28	92.00	8.00	1.20	18.80	0.60	18.80
Jharsuguda	33.67	40.00	77.00	2.13	12.50	1.25	12.50
Kendujhar	52.25	80.53	53.47	1.16	2.11	0.11	2.11
Sambalpur	60.59	1000.00	-800.00	20.00	180.00	20.00	180.00
Sundargarh	56.28	200.00	170.00	7.00	35.00	4.60	35.00

Sources: Computed by the author with Database of Odisha State Dashboard

Table 2 shows the healthcare beds availability in the southern division. The total number of beds for per centre is the highest in Ganjam followed by Nuapada, Koraput, Gajapati, Nabarangapur, Malkangiri and the lowest in Rayagada districts. In the remaining five parameters all districts are similarly placed except Koraput and Nuapada where total ICU beds per Centres and total beds per TMC are a little bit high.

Table 2: COVID-19 Healthcare Beds Availability in Southern Division of Odisha

District	Number of beds per TMC	Number of beds per centre	Difference between bed capacity and total beds	ICU beds per centre	Isolation beds per centre	Number of ventilator beds per centre	Oxygen beds per centre
Boudh	39.89	134.00	-18.00	0.00	60.00	0.00	42.50
Gajapati	97.11	200.00	-100.00	0.00	50.00	0.00	20.00
Ganjam	48.00	435.86	-235.86	2.86	25.71	2.86	25.71
Kalahandi	38.19	100.00	100.00	0.60	19.00	0.60	6.60
Kandhamal	63.24	155.70	-5.70	0.00	14.00	0.10	1.00
Koraput	40.74	200.00	-50.00	4.00	147.00	3.00	50.00
Malkangiri	55.46	150.00	-50.00	2.00	48.00	3.00	35.00
Nabarangpur	56.15	166.00	34.00	1.67	66.67	0.33	66.67
Nuapada	40.43	400.00	-400.00	0.00	195.00	5.00	160.00
Rayagada	71.52	100.00	0.00	0.00	16.67	0.00	16.67

Sources: Computed by the author with Database of Odisha State Dashboard

Table 3 shows the healthcare beds availability in the central division. While the total number of beds per centre is the highest in Jajapur, total isolation beds per centre is led by Khordha and followed by Jajapur, Cuttack and Nayagarh.

Table 3: COVID-19 Healthcare Beds Availability in Central Division of Odisha

District	Number of beds per TMC	Number of beds per centre	Difference between bed capacity and total beds	Total ICU beds per centre	Total isolation beds per centre	Number of ventilators beds per centre	Total oxygen beds per centre
Baleswar	33.70	124.00	-4.00	2.40	18.00	1.00	10.00
Bhadrak	100.08	120.00	0.00	0.40	11.60	0.40	2.00
Cuttack	36.43	100.00	50.00	40.00	116.00	8.00	116.00
Jagatsinghapur	33.48	75.00	0.00	1.25	11.25	0.75	5.00

Jajapur	31.23	400.00	-250.00	10.00	140.00	3.00	100.00
Kendrapara	44.30	91.11	18.89	1.00	11.11	0.56	0.00
Khordha	65.16	150.00	875.00	35.00	465.00	32.50	465.00
Mayurbhanj	41.96	57.54	142.46	0.38	7.31	0.15	0.50
Nayagarh	38.57	51.67	148.33	0.00	63.33	1.67	26.67
Puri	37.50	101.33	98.67	0.00	6.67	0.00	1.67
Sonepur	27.50	45.50	154.50	1.67	16.67	0.00	4.17

Sources: Computed by the author with Database of Odisha State Dashboard

Table 4 presents the information on average (of all the 30 districts) of availability of beds at COVID-19 centres. In order to respond to large number of cases, it would be useful to increase the number of ICU beds per centre to 10 and the number of ventilator beds per centre to 10 also.

Table4: COVID-19 Average Hospital Bed Availability at the District Level in Odisha

Number of Beds	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Error	Std. Deviation
Beds per TMC	27.5	100.08	49.47	3.29	18.04
Beds per centre	40	1000	178.39	33.77	184.98
ICU beds per centre	0	40	4.86	1.78	9.75
Isolation beds per centre	2.11	465	67.55	16.83	92.17
Ventilator beds per centre	0	32.5	3.22	1.23	6.74
Oxygen beds per centre	0	465	49.54	16.63	91.09

Sources: Computed by the author with Database of Odisha State Dashboard

Odisha is preparing itself to become the first state in the country to have a dedicated COVID-19 healthcare facility in each of its 30 districts with combined bed strength of 6000. The state govt. is now looking to create 34,000 beds in the COVID-19 care centres form among the TMC and ICUs have been projected 2386 beds and oxygen supported facilities 6141 beds. The bed projection is likely to go up with a gradual rise in the number of affected districts. As of now, Odisha has reported to sensing that creating additional beds will not serve the purpose, the health department has been directed to create an inventory of human resources to be required in these facilities (Kapoor & Mangla, 2020).

Managing the COVID-19 Crisis

The WHO Country Office for India has been working closely with the MoHFW

on preparedness and reaction measures for COVID-19, including surveillance and contact following, laboratory diagnosis, risk communications and community engagement, hospital preparedness, infection prevention and control, and adherence to regulations. Efforts have been stepped up to pursue measures to find, isolate, test, treat and follow.

Decentralized Information Campaigns: The first state-wide information, education and communication (IEC) outreach about the Coronavirus in Odisha was conducted on March 8, 2020 the day when the first international passenger was screened in the state. Two days later, the state government declared COVID-19 to be a 'disaster' and public officials were empowered to contain the spread under the Disaster Management Act, 2005. It is perhaps too early to isolate the reason for containment of COVID-19 in Odisha, but timely on-ground preparedness and decentralized information campaigns have mattered. Overall, Odisha's strategy has been considered appropriate in managing the pandemic (HFWO, 2020a).

WhatsApp Helpdesk: The Government of Odisha has started a chatbot on WhatsApp to respond to the queries of people. The chatbot has been named MyGov Corona Helpdesk. It aims to make citizens aware of the pandemic and keep them away from myths and misinformation. A single portal information system was set up with a dedicated spokesperson to provide clear information and discrete instructions to the public at a press meet which took place every day. Clear guidelines on 'what to do' and 'what not to do' were detailed. There was strict regulation on disclosure of identity and information management (Labana, 2020; HFWO, 2020a).

Efficient Work Delivery: The police personnel, healthcare workers and the government had delineated responsibilities. The health officials were not directly involved in public information management, to let them focus on their work. The police took a lead role in enforcing the lockdown and strict distancing norms (Sarita and Datta, 2020). The state government announced several welfare resources to address the difficulties being faced by people during the lockdown. Advance disbursement of these resources was done to the entitled beneficiaries, including pensioners (4 month's pension), ration card holders (3 month's ration) and students (scholarships). Provision of food for the sick, indigent and destitute in rural areas was ensured (Loiwal & Suffian, 2020).

Designated COVID Hospitals and Capacity Building of Healthcare Workers: Odisha had planned for exclusive COVID-19 healthcare facilities early on by setting

up 'Coronavirus hospitals' across the state forging partnership with existing non-government hospitals, including medical colleges and private hospitals. Odisha set an example by creating the first and the largest COVID-19 hospital in India (Labana, 2020; HFWO, 2020b). Online training programmes for healthcare personnel and medical students and advance disbursement of salaries for all healthcare personnel in the state was initiated. To provide informed healthcare in the state, about 500 faculty members and staff of medical institutions, 1600 medical officers of AYUSH, and about 900 residents and faculty members of dental colleges were trained in basic management through video-conferencing apps. Among frontline health workers, about 5542 nursing students, 1.17 lakh ASHAs and auxiliary nurse midwives were trained online.

Collective Efforts by the Government and People

The state government had arranged for sample testing facilities spread across the state and this had helped identifying cases and also to follow ICMR guidelines for isolating people and taking appropriate need-based steps to prevent the spread of the virus. The temporary medical centres in villages had done an excellent job in checking the scatter of the virus and about 95 per cent of Odisha's positive cases were reported from quarantine centres (Saikia, 2017). This demonstrated the collective efforts put by sarpanches, individual agents and the government apparatus. At the Gram Panchayat level the Sarpanch ensured registration of those who arrived in the village and, if required, sent them for 14 days to stay in the quarantine centre equipped with facilities like accommodation, food, sanitation etc. In addition to observe some health check-up protocols as screening, testing etc. following the stay period financial incentives were also provided by the government.

State Leadership: Odisha played a lead role in extending the lockdown in the initial phase and it was also unique in introducing the complete weekend shutdown in the state after the nationwide lockdown was withdrawn; this acted as a potential preventive measure. Odisha's solution-based approach, with flexible and dynamic state leadership attaching minimal importance to political gains helped strengthen the centre-state collaboration ensuring the best possible outcomes (HFWO, 2020a; Sarita & Datta, 2020). Financial and organizational support was provided to Gram Panchayats ensuring provision for temporary medical camps with extensive information campaigns on COVID-19, its prevention and case reporting by Swachhta Sathis (Sanitation Workers) at Zila Parishad (District Council) level were emphasized (Sarita & Datta, 2020).

Returnee Migrants: Before the lockdown alert Odisha had prepared a database of returnee migrants and recorded the first case in the state. On the day of the national lockdown, the state government knew 78,233 persons had returned to Odisha from other states, with district and Panchayat specific information. The data was shared with Gram Panchayats and the Panchayat Samiti and district administration were intimated about those arrivals. Through IEC, the state had already prepared Panchayat members towards encouraging returnee migrants to self-isolate or quarantine, with cash incentives. A database of all persons arriving in Odisha from other states was activated. Provision of roadside Jalachhatras (sheds to offer drinking water and refreshments), temporary shelters and food, etc. and mobile healthcare units was ensured (Sarita & Datta, 2020; HFWO, 2020a).

Infection Control, COVID Testing and Contact Tracing: It was made compulsory to use face masks while stepping out of the house for any reason. Testing had been broad-based and as on May 5, 2020 Odisha had conducted 723 tests for per million people, much above the national corresponding figure of around 519. Stringent containment and contact tracing measures were followed and sharing of area data of mobile uses identifying confirmed/suspect cases of COVID-19 was undertaken (Sarita & Datta, 2020).

Participation of NGOs: In addition to the measures of the state government, various initiatives were taken at individual and community levels by volunteers and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). In many places volunteers, in turns, closely monitored the entry of any outsiders and ensured mandatory screening and notification. A few NGOs had come forward to provide shelter, food baskets and hygiene kits to the needy; providing masks and refreshments to the police officials and other workers who were on duty. Some individuals and organisations had donated masks, sanitizers, PPEs, etc. to the healthcare institutions (HFWO, 2020a).

Conclusion

Despite being a less developed state, Odisha's efforts in managing the COVID-19 crisis has been widely appreciated because of the low death rates and high recovery rates. Odisha has spent enormously in the health sector particularly in connection with COVID management after lockdown. The economy has shown signs of improvement inspite of many challenges. A negative economic growth would imply less revenue collection and limited fiscal space for the

Odisha government. Nevertheless, the state government is required to implement feasible health policies by allocating a higher share of the budget for the health sector.

The daily recoveries and releases from hospitals and TMCs during the crisis period outnumbered the positive cases. The community cooperation through Panchayat Raj Institutions (PRIs) and self-help groups (SHGs) has been an important element in this achievement. The TMCs and quarantine centre were being ably overseen at the Panchayat level through the dynamic support of the Sarpanchs, chosen delegates, SHGs and the concerned individuals. It could be argued that COVID-19 never spiked in Odisha, a state not exactly known for an effective health system. From the beginning, the response of the state to the pandemic has seen increased testing, effective resource allocation, swift private sector partnerships, infrastructure build-up, capacity building of human resources in healthcare, and incentives for citizens to opt for tests. All these initiatives would have resulted in a low case confirmation ratio, low case fatality rate, high recovery and discharge ratio. Odisha's COVID-19 management strategy could offer insights into effective pandemic management now and in future.

However, the future is not without a few challenges in terms of containing the spread of the Coronavirus in the state and managing people's restlessness due to limits set on development activities. Reviving the economy and providing appropriate work and food to poor people remain major concerns.

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